

PYTHON ALGORITHMIC LANGUAGE , CREATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF QUESTION-ANSWER SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: This article is about information technology. Today, information is not only necessary information, but also a commodity of great value.

Collecting, storing, processing and delivering them to the right place is the main goal and task of information technologies.

Keywords: Information technologies, virtual,informatics and information technologies,intellectual system

It is not for nothing that the 21st century is called the century of informatics and information technology. Because today information is not only necessary information, but also a commodity with great value. Their collection, storage, processing and delivery to the right place is the main goal and task of information technology. Intelligent systems are a central part of information technology.

Intelligent systems can also be divided into several parts. One of these parts is the system of questions and answers. This system, in turn, may consist of the following:

- ❖ Intelligent Search Engines
- ❖ Virtual Digital Assistants
- ❖ Virtual interlocutors (VS)

The following is general information about the system of virtual interlocutors of the system of questions and answers. Next, we consider several technologies for their creation.

The system of questions and answers plays an important role in the development of models of human interaction with a computer. Modeling of question-answer systems allows you to create a wider and more convenient communication between a person and a computer in natural language. When using these systems, a person has the opportunity to receive answers to his questions in real time.

Therefore, the creation of systems capable of presenting this data in an understandable form, that is, in natural language, is one of the modern and urgent tasks of informatics and information technology. The closer the language in which the question-answer system is used to the spoken language, the easier it is for a person to use this system and build a dialogue with it. One of the most important tasks of the system is to get an answer to a question asked by the user in natural language.

Virtual chats are usually organized in the form of sites. In this case, the intelligent system communicates with users via text chat. Each individually created aircraft system has its own visual interface, which is able to convey the feeling of the system to the user and make communication with the interlocutor more personal and reliable.

The structure of virtual interlocutors can be as follows:

- ❖ The first component of the aircraft is the user interface through which the user interacts with the aircraft. The user interface is a dialog box with a text input line, a system response line, informational remarks and its visual representation.

- ❖ The second component of the system is a complex platform that determines the behavior and vocabulary of the VS. It contains a system knowledge base (that is, a set of flexible scripts with built-in questions and answers). In addition, the

system enriches its knowledge base with information about the customer, his needs and desires.

The aircraft can be used as an intelligent system that replaces the services of the following specialists:

- ❖ consultants answering users' questions about the offered goods and services;
- ❖ sales assistants helping to choose the right product, service, tariff, etc.;
- ❖ technical assistants that help the user solve technical problems;
- ❖ promoters promoting new goods and services;
- ❖ interesting interlocutors that arouse interest, increase the mood and loyalty of visitors.

Application areas of the system:

1. Banks and insurance companies, where it is important to have a qualified consultant who can quickly, intelligibly and clearly tell all the information about the services provided;
2. online stores that care about helping customers in choosing goods, as well as about promotions and sales;
3. Internet portals that should focus users' attention on their internal projects;
4. Organizers of events for whom it is important to inform site visitors about all the news and details;
5. Repair companies that require 24/7 customer support.

The advantages of virtual interlocutors include its effectiveness, ease of use, and others.

As mentioned above, the interface of the aircraft systems in the form of a web page can be formed using the Flash software, based on the memory dictionary and knowledge base, and the formation of intelligent information can be formed in the form of a local system using the PHP algorithmic language. This is a relatively complex and complex process.

The world's first online question and answer system is called START (SynTactic Analysis using reversible Transformations), developed by Boris Katz at the Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and has been in continuous operation since December 1993 [1]. Currently, the system can answer millions of English-language questions about places, movies, people, and more.

At present, the use of modern technologies that store databases (knowledge) of computer science and information technology in the clouds is widespread. There are several types of paid (and free) cloud computing services, and there are many companies and organizations offering them to users [2,3]. One such organization is Google. At the same time, the technology for implementing an intelligent question-answer system using Google services (database and knowledge) was created on the basis of one of the modules of the modern algorithmic language Python [4].

The question-answer technology works according to the following algorithm (Fig. 1.):

Rice. 1. Algorithm of technology question-answer system

Below is a code snippet of speech recognition using SpeechRecognition and PyAudio modules in Python language :

```
import speech_recognition as sr
recognizer = sr.Recognizer ()
with sr.Microphone () as source:
    print( "Adjusting noise ")
    recognizer.adjust_for_ambient_noise (source, duration=1)
    print( "Recording for 4 seconds")
    recorded_audio = recognizer.listen (source, timeout=4)
    print( "Done recording")
try:
    print( "Recognizing the text")
    text = recognizer.recognize_google (
        recorded_audio ,
        language=" en -US"
    )
    print( "Decoded Text : {}".format(text))
except Exception as ex:
    print(ex)
```

The above program works in interactive mode and invites you to say something on the microphone. Further, the program recognizes the speech spoken in English and what you said gives a text format in the form:

```
Adjusting noise
Recording for 4 seconds
```


Done recording

Recognizing the text

result2:

```
{ 'alternative': [ {'confidence': 0.98762906, 'transcript': 'hello'} ],
'final': True }
```

Decoded Text : hello

The authors have created a "Question and Answer" system that helps the buyer find the right hangers in large supermarkets based on the above Python modules.

This information system recognizes questions asked through a microphone, extracts "key" words from it and gives a logical answer in audio format, based on a knowledge base in memory.

Thus, based on the above, we can conclude that:

6. Intelligent systems are a central part of information technology;
7. One of the most important tasks of the system is to get an answer to a question asked by the user in natural language;
8. The creation and implementation of programs such as "Virtual Interlocutor" is easily and quickly carried out using the algorithmic language Python and its modules.

List of used literature

1. <http://start.csail.mit.edu/index.php>
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